

The Kinetics and Mechanism of Substitution of Chloride Ion in *Trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]Cl by Parahydroxy Benzoic Acid

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The steric course of the Cl⁻ ion substitution in *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ by *p*-hydroxy benzoate ion was studied in 15% (v/v) ethanol at pH 3 and at 30°. A mechanism has been proposed. Convincing proof for the proposed mechanism was obtained by comparing the spectrophotometrically obtained values of concentration of the different species at different times (during the course of the reaction) with the corresponding values calculated using the rate constants. The rate constants were determined by a combination of potentiometric and spectrophotometric methods and studying the reaction part by part.

In a previous communication¹ to this journal we have shown that substitution of Cl⁻ ion in *cis*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ by parahydroxybenzoate ion (B₂⁻) proceeds through the formation of a pentacoordinate intermediate which then competitively captures both water and B₂⁻ producing simultaneously *cis* and *trans* aquo complexes [Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺ and *cis*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]⁺; at the same time equilibrium between *cis* and *trans* aquo complexes and between *cis*-aquo and *cis*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]⁺ are established. As a continuation of this work we are now reporting the mechanism of substitution of Cl⁻ ion in *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ by B₂⁻, under the same experimental conditions i.e., in 15% (v/v) ethanol (pH=3) and at 30°. The present work shows that unlike *cis*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺, *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ is not directly attacked by B₂⁻; on the contrary here *cis*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]⁺ is produced by the reaction of B₂⁻ with *cis*-[Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺, which is directly produced from *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺. The total reaction is found to follow the scheme :

Incidentally it may be mentioned here that Brown and Ingold² have reported direct substitution of chloro group in *cis*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ by some basic anions in methanol medium and Pearson *et al*³ have reported that in the same medium no direct substitution occurs in *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ by basic anions.

Experimental

Preparation of compounds : *Trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]Cl was prepared by the method given in the literature⁴. *Cis*-[Coen₂H₂OCl]SO₄ · 1.5H₂O was prepared by the method of Werner⁵. The ligand used was ammonium parahydroxybenzoate, prepared by the reaction of (NH₄)₂CO₃ and *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid.

Characterisation of products : Both *trans*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]B₂ · 7H₂O and *cis*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]Cl are found to be produced by the reaction of *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]Cl with NH₄B₂⁻. However, under our experimental conditions only *cis*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]Cl is found to be produced¹. To see the possibility of formation of any *trans*-[Coen₂B₂Cl]⁺ we mixed methanolic solutions of A and HB₂ and after a long time took the spectrum of the mixture. This was identical with the spectrum of A, meaning that no new complex had been produced.

Study of the kinetics : The total reaction of Cl⁻ ion substitution in A by B₂⁻ was followed in six parts (a) to (f) discussed below.

[All these studies were carried out in 15% (v/v) ethanol (pH=3) at 30°.]

(a) **Potentiometric determination of Cl⁻ ion release in A, in presence and absence of B₂⁻ :** The rate of Cl⁻ release from A, both in presence and absence of B₂⁻ was determined potentiometrically. The process was the same as described in our previous communication¹. It was found that the rate constant (k) for the Cl⁻ release was the same both in presence and absence of B₂⁻ (k = 6.67 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹). This result suggests that the first step in the reaction is a slow dissociative step resulting in the formation of the pentacoordinate intermediate [Coen₂Cl]⁺ as was the case with *cis* isomer¹.

(b) *Isomerisation of cis-[Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺ into trans form:*

The study of this equilibrium has been reported earlier¹. The values of k_3 and k_4 ($k_3 = 0.44 \times 10^{-4}/\text{sec}$ and $k_4 = 1.09 \times 10^{-4}/\text{sec}$) obtained there are utilised here for calculation.

(c) *Spectrophotometric study of the aquation of A:* That aquation of A follows the scheme—

Scheme 2

was observed by Baldwin *et al*⁶, who however have not determined the values of k_1 and k_2 . We have determined these values and our method was as follows. Spectral data shows that at 490 nm $\epsilon_A = \epsilon_C = 14$ and $\epsilon_B = 72$, hence the concentration B_t of B produced at any time 't' during aquation can be known from the change in O.D. value at this wavelength. The concentration C_t of C at any time 't' was calculated from the relation

$$Cl_t = A_0 + B_t + C_t$$

where Cl_t = total chloride ion at time t obtained potentiometrically and A_0 = initial concentration of A.

Now from the potentiometric study (a) the overall rate constant k for the chloride release reaction was found out. It is evident that this k is the sum of two individual rate constants k_1 and k_2 for the parallel reactions $A \rightarrow B$ and $A \rightarrow C$ respectively (Scheme 1), i.e.,

$$k = k_1 + k_2$$

Had there been no interconversion between B and C the ratio k_2/k_1 would have been equal to C_t/B_t at any time 't'. But the value of C_t/B_t gradually departs from k_2/k_1 because of this interconversion. We have therefore plotted C_t/B_t against time (Fig. 1) and extrapolated it to zero time, so that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} C_t/B_t = k_2/k_1 = 1.7 \text{ (from Fig. 1)}$$

The individual rate constants k_1 and k_2 were calculated out from the value of k_2/k_1 thus obtained and the value of $k = k_2 + k_1$ determined by the study 'a'. [$k_1 = 2.47 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$ and $k_2 = 4.20 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$].

Fig. 1. Plot of C_t/B_t (Exptl.) against t.

(d+e) *Spectrophotometric studies of (d) entry of B_z^- in B and (e) aquation of 'D':*

The studies of the above reactions have been reported in our previous communication¹. The values of k_5 and k_6 reported there are utilised here for calculation [$k_5 = 1.76 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$ and $k_6 = 0.50 \times 10^{-4}/\text{sec}$].

(f) *Spectrophotometric study of the entry of B_z^- in A:* Since B_z^- does not react directly with A, (vide 'characterisation of products) and C appears not to react with B_z^- (ref. 1), but B reacts with B_z^- to give D, it is believed that during the course of the reaction, the reaction mixture contains A, B, C and D only (see Scheme 1). In order to determine the concentrations B_t , C_t , D_t and unreacted A, at any time 't' during the entry of B_z^- in A we studied the reaction spectrophotometrically at three different wave-lengths which were 460 nm, 490 nm and 560 nm.

At 460 nm $\epsilon_A \approx \epsilon_B = \epsilon_C = 29$ and $\epsilon_D = 73$; hence increase in O.D. will give the concentration of D at any time. We could not however, detect any O.D. change of the reaction mixture upto first 90 minutes, after which O.D. changes, but the change was so small that the concentration of D could not be calculated with accuracy. This led us to the belief that D is not produced directly from A, but it is produced from B and as this formation occurs at a very slow rate¹, the O.D. change was very small. Accordingly, the complete reaction scheme was provisionally formulated as given in Scheme 1.

At 490 nm $\epsilon_A = \epsilon_C = 14$ and $\epsilon_D \approx \epsilon_B = 72$. So the sum of concentrations of B (i.e. B_t) and D (i.e. D_t) at any time 't' will be known from the equation—

$$\Delta d_t = (\epsilon_B - \epsilon_A) \cdot \frac{(B_t + D_t)}{A_0}$$

where $\Delta d_t = (\text{O.D. of the reaction mixture at time 't' minus O.D. of A at concentration } A_0) \div (\text{length of the cell} \times A_0)$ and $A_0 = \text{Initial concentration of A}$.

At 560 nm again $\epsilon_A = 16$, $\epsilon_C = 25$ and $\epsilon_B \approx \epsilon_D = 63$, hence C_t will be known from the equation—

$$\Delta d_t' = (\epsilon_B - \epsilon_A) \cdot \frac{(B_t + D_t)}{A_0} + (\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A) \cdot \frac{C_t}{A_0}$$

$(B_t + D_t)$ being already known, C_t will be known from this equation.

The concentration of unreacted A, i.e., A_t at any moment will be known from the equation—

$$A_0 = A_t + B_t + C_t + D_t$$

We could not however determine the individual values of B_t and D_t at any time 't'.

Results and Discussion

We started our study by following the aquation of A in absence of B_z^- using a combination of spectrophotometric and potentiometric methods (studies 'b' and 'a'). Experimentally we have determined the concentrations B_t and C_t at any time 't'. We then theoretically calculated the concentrations B_t and C_t from the experimental k_1 , k_2 , k_3 and k_4 values (Scheme 2) and following an approximate method of calculation reported in our earlier communication¹. The agreement (Table 1) between theoretical and experimental values are very good.

We then tried to propose a scheme for the reaction of entry of B_z^- in A. As we have seen that B_z^- does not attack A directly and *cis*-substituted product D is produced by the reaction of B_z^- with B alone and not from A, we proposed the Scheme 1

TABLE 1—(AQUATION OF A)
T=30°; pH=3; SOLVENT=15% (v/v) Ethanol,
INITIAL CONCENTRATION=0.01(M)

Time (Mins.)	Concentration of B(B_t)		Concentration of C(C_t)		C_t/B_t (Exptl.)
	Found $\times 10^4$ (M)	Calcd. $\times 10^4$ (M)	Found $\times 10^4$ (M)	Calcd. $\times 10^4$ (M)	
10	0.16	0.15	0.24	0.25	1.5
20	0.32	0.30	0.40	0.48	1.3
30	0.49	0.46	0.60	0.68	1.2
40	0.62	0.62	0.70	0.80	1.13
50	0.74	0.76	0.80	0.90	1.08
60	0.99	0.95	1.01	1.10	1.02
70	1.15	1.10	1.10	1.20	0.956

for this reaction. This scheme was established in the following way.

Spectrophotometrically we have determined $(B_t + D_t)$ and C_t at any time 't'. Next according to the Scheme 1 we calculated the concentrations of A_t , B_t , C_t and D_t using the experimentally determined values of the rate constants k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , k_4 , k_5 and k_6 at any time following an approximate method of calculation reported earlier¹. The results are given in Table 2. It will be seen from the table that the agreement between calculated and experimental values of C_t and A_t are very good. It is also seen that upto first 90 minutes, the theoretical values of B_t are almost equal to the experimental $(B_t + D_t)$ values and after then the theoretical values of B_t become little less than experimental $(B_t + D_t)$ values. This observation supports our scheme, in which it has been visualised that D is produced only from B at a very slow rate, and not at all from A. The scheme gets further support from the fact that the total chloride ion calculated from the experimental (spectrophotometrically found) values of A_t , $(B_t + D_t)$ and C_t tallies very well with the total chloride ion determined by independent potentiometric study.

TABLE 2—ENTRY OF B_z^- IN A

T=30°; pH=3; SOLVENT=15% (v/v) ETHANOL; INITIAL CONCENTRATION OF A=0.01(M);

CONCENTRATION OF $NH_4B_z^- = 0.1(M)$

CONCENTRATIONS ARE IN (M) $\times 10^3$

Time (Mins.)	Exptl. ($B_t + D_t$)	Calcd. B_t	Calcd. D_t	Exptl. C_t	Calcd. C_t	Exptl. A_t	Calcd. A_t	Spectrophotometric Cl_t	Potentiometric Cl_t
30	0.46	0.45	—	0.78	0.76	8.7	8.8	11.2	11.1
60	1.00	0.948	0.0014	1.30	1.308	7.7	7.7	12.2	12.0
90	1.60	1.47	0.005	1.68	1.71	6.7	6.8	13.16	13.3
120	2.21	1.99	0.009	2.01	2.005	5.9	6.0	14.01	14.5
150	2.70	2.49	0.014	2.29	2.22	5.0	5.3	14.75	15.1
180	3.10	2.96	0.021	2.50	2.38	4.3	4.6	15.32	15.4

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